

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports the interactions of the SIMCor consortium with regulatory stakeholders at this point (M18) of the SIMCor project. Those interactions were facilitated via a dedicated SIMCor Regulatory Advisory Board (RAB) meeting or via a continuous liaison between regulators and the in-silico community at large via the VPH partner. The outcomes of the discussions are reported here, and conclusions are derived for future actions and directions.

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TABLE 1: REGULATORY ADVISORY BOARD 5

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AA	Avicenna Alliance
BIO	Biotronik
CHA	Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin
COU	Context of Use
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GSP	Good Simulation Practice
IHS	Institut für Höhere Studien – Institute for Advanced Studies
IIB	Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V.
LYN	Lynkeus
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
MDDT	Medical Device Development Tools
NB	Notified Body
PHI	Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.
RAB	Regulatory Advisory Board
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TUE	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven
TUG	Technical University Graz
UCL	University College of London
UTBV	Universitatea Transilvania Din Braşov
VC	Virtual Cohort
VPH	Virtual Physiological institute

Introduction

Objective O1 of SIMCor is to develop standard protocols and validation workflow that will help integrate computer modelling solutions into the regulatory approval process while objective O4 is to accelerate the adoption and integration of computer simulations in the regulatory evaluation of medical devices through dissemination of results, increasing trust of users and community building. Hence, regular, and in-depth interactions with regulatory authorities is needed to achieve those objectives.

The task T2.3 of SIMCor is devoted to liaison with regulatory authorities in the healthcare sector, particularly regarding the design, development, piloting, clinical validation, and benchmarking of medical devices. This activity is carried out leveraging the contacts of VPH with EMA and the Memorandum of Understanding between the Avicenna Alliance (AA) and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) - working on Good Simulation Practices -, as well as contacts with Notified Bodies (NB) and the in-silico medicine community at large. SIMCor seeks to involve authorities in the development of SOPs and the conduction of iterative feedback cycles regarding design of virtual cohort (VC) generation, device effect simulation model validation and translation into the clinical setting. The plan is to discuss, agree and introduce recommendations and guidelines throughout the project implementation, with round ups at regular project milestones.

The point of the work carried by SIMCor is to open-up the dialogue with regulatory authorities and identify a path in which the type of in silico approach we propose could be used in regulatory submissions for medical device approval. The SIMCor simulations concern the bench testing, pre-clinical and clinical assessment of medical devices. The exemplar cases of TAVI and PAPS (cardiac medical devices) were chosen but by no means the project is intending to collect advice for a company-specific product.

This deliverable is to report the first rounds of regulatory stakeholders' consultation, whether through the dedicated SIMCor Regulatory Advisory Board (RAB) or through the continuous liaison between regulators and the in-silico community at large via VPH. The first part of that document summarises the feedback obtained during the RAB meeting held in June 2022, the second part reports other on-going discussions with various regulatory authorities.

Regulatory Advisory Board meeting

The advisory board

The advisory board is composed of experts from non-partners regulatory organisations who are at stake in the healthcare and medical device sector. The notified body TÜV SÜD was represented by Jan Kürfner and the FDA was represented by Dr Prasanna Hariharan.

Name	Function	Organization name	Organization type
Jan Kürfner	Senior Product Specialist for Cybersecurity of Medical Devices, Product Specialist, Lead Auditor.	TÜV SÜD	Notified body
Dr. Prasanna Hariharan	Deputy Director, Division of Applied Mechanics (DAM) Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories (OSEL) Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH)	FDA	National health regulatory authority

Table 1: Regulatory Advisory Board

Methodology

The board members were invited to an online meeting on the day following the General Assembly, June 15th, 2022. The agenda included a general presentation about SIMCor, a presentation about the virtual cohort generation and validation, a presentation about the virtual device modelling and simulation and a presentation about the standard operating procedures (SOP). The detailed Agenda with the list of attendees is available in **Appendix I**.

A month before the meeting, the Board received a summary about the SIMCor project (M1-M18 activities) together with the Deliverables regarding SOPs. A list of questions was prepared by the SIMCor partners to feed the discussion on the points of interest (**Appendix II**).

Feedback summary

Prasanna Hariharan (FDA)

About the virtual cohort and virtual device simulation, Dr Hariharan enquired about the computational platform: what is the goal of SIMCor with that platform? Is there a plan to get a CE MDD certification¹? To this question, the consortium replied that submitting the platform is a longer-term objective but at the moment mock submissions for the intermediate outputs such as the virtual cohort, and the in-silico models could be considered.

The virtual cohort in itself is not a medical device, but it could get a certification as a tool used during development of medical devices. This procedure is called Medical Device Development Tools (MDDT) at FDA². Dr Prasanna encouraged SIMCor to apply at FDA to get direct feedback on the content of the virtual cohort generation methodology. The feedback for a particular tool is given considering its specific intended use, which must be clearly defined and stated in the application. With FDA it is possible to engage very early, without too much effort to initiate the process. This way most of the

¹ https://www.gpc.center/ce_mdd_/581

² <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-device-development-tools-mddt>

discussions happen at the pre-submission stage. However, applications for the MDDT must be done for tools that may apply to a family of devices but not to a company-specific device. Indeed, the procedure is not meant to get feedback on a product but on a method to assess and develop a type of device.

In the case of SIMCor, we are working with two very high-risk devices, which might be more challenging with respect to in-silico evaluation. However, only the MDDT application will tell us whether FDA deem the use of in-silico methods in combination with virtual cohorts feasible or not.

Regarding the possibility to replace clinical studies with virtual cohorts, the answer will be very case-dependent. It depends on the type of devices, the availability of alternative methods on the market and the target population. As an engineering expert in regulatory issues, the representative of FDA truly sees the potential of such computational approaches; however, when it comes to clinical trials, the medical officers and biostatisticians have a big influence on the decision whether an in-silico study can partially or fully replace any clinical studies. Hence, clinical stakeholders, including from regulatory authorities, should be involved in the discussion.

Dr Hariharan acknowledges that using virtual cohorts is revolutionary, but also disruptive: the complexity is so high that using this technology to help design a clinical study would be a lower bar than fully replacing a clinical study, for the moment. Although, even for that intended purpose, the application will likely require recurrent exchanges with FDA.

He also encouraged us to consult example tools that have been approved (some computational), which are available on their website, to see what type of computational tools could be considered regulatory sufficient.

About the submitted SOPs and standardisation efforts, we were informed that the V&V40 working group also has a sub-group working on image-based modelling, which might be of interest for us. One aspect for which they see an unmet need is related to the high user variability that exists for geometry reconstruction, having a simple workflow to do that would be of great value. When it comes to standardisation, we still must come a long way to achieve a standard for that. A lot of what we are developing with the SOPs can fall into that effort. Something that is also missing now in the ASME is a document guiding how to deal with the high levels of uncertainty in the input and boundary conditions.

More precisely, looking at the SOP for data processing, it resembles more general recommendations. The recommendation from FDA would be to focus more on how to minimise errors and uncertainty. How can we reduce and quantify errors in this step to avoid propagation in the modelling process? That is something missing in general and of interest in the view of FDA. The work of SIMCor could contribute to meet that need. However, these aspects are currently investigated in the deliverables on the uncertainty quantification, as for example D7.5, where methods for assessing the propagation of errors throughout the processing pipeline were investigated, to identify the most robust sets of input parameters, allowing calculation of the parameters of interest with the highest accuracy possible.

As recommendations for the SOP on VC and validation, we got feedback that giving general considerations was a good starting point, but the SOPs developed so far were not prescriptive enough, meaning that they offer suggestions rather than rules that must be adhered to. The multi-stage/multi-level validation procedure for the VC is a sound strategy and we should investigate the work of Oberkamp³ on hierarchy validation. FDA would be curious about our way to assess if and how much errors in the lower level propagate in the other levels for the validation.

³ <https://cfwebprod.sandia.gov/cfdocs/CompResearch/docs/Oberkampf-Trucano-SAND2007-0853.pdf>

Outside the regulatory context, there is a large interest when SIMCor talks about standardisation and joint publication activities with FDA. There would be several people interested at FDA in working with us on some of the standard operating procedures. In particular, the virtual cohort generation and validation procedure are of interest. Dr Hariharan can be our contact, identifying interested colleagues at the FDA. In addition, MDDT is not company or product specific so we could work with FDA fellows on the MDDT submission, but this requires more work. Overall, it is a better strategy to work outside the regulatory context and focus on standard operating procedures and publications if we want to collaborate with FDA early on.

Minimal level of dissemination: FDA thinks it is a good idea to publish the SOPs. FDA would be interested in contributing (e.g., for journals such as ASME journal VVUQ) but we should provide more details on the error minimization.

About the model development for TAVI and PAPS, it was emphasised again that there might be issues of cancellation errors when using clinical evidence for validation. Intermediate validation (e.g., show the ability to estimate physical metrics) might be needed before applying the model to virtual cohorts and comparing the outcome to clinical endpoints. Some of the questions of interest the consortium attempts to answer, such as the durability risk, paravalvular leakage or risk of thrombosis are long-term risks and are very complicated to model. There are factors such as the drug device interaction that can have an impact, for instance on the risk of thrombosis. The consortium response to the validation of long-term risk is that it is possible to identify surrogate parameters that we can correlate with the long-term risk. The consortium is also considering implementing methods to study sub-cohorts (different age groups, etc.).

Dr Hariharan stated that the computational cardiovascular model we presented was impressive and we, as a community, including the regulators, must find out how we can best assess credibility of those important models.

Regarding the question on the relation between the risk assessment and credibility activities (what is the right level of credibility for the right level of risk), the answer was that it is impossible to define a risk if there is no context of use (COU). The risk can only be assessed with information related to the COU, such as the other types of evidence that exist in the relevant regulation.

Jan Kűfner (TűV SűD)

About the virtual cohort and virtual device simulation: The consortium was seeking for feedback about the proposed CM&S-based evaluation method for cardiovascular medical device approval. The consortium was informed that as per MDCG 2022-14 TűV SűD is welcoming open dialogue before conformity assessments for In-Silico testing since this methodology has the potential to improve benefits for patients.

The consortium clarified that the aim was not to submit or promote any medical device but that it was rather to assess whether the type of computational evidence the consortium is producing could be considered in an accreditation process, in general.

A general discussion on this topic is also likely to enhance the efficiency and predictability of the conformity assessment process while respecting the independence and impartiality of the notified body.

A key question to be discussed about the proposed approach is whether it intends to replace entirely a typical clinical evaluation report for a medical device application or simply, complement it. In other words, the specific context of use should be better specified. This type of questions should typically involve clinical opinion leaders from NBs. For TűV SűD bringing computational evidence on top of the regular evidence would be fine: more data and evidence is always welcome. However, for replacing

portions of the clinical evaluation report this would depend on how much and which part of the study and of the clinical evaluation report is replaced. The consortium was recommended to send its requirements and describe what parts of the certification studies is proposed to be replace so that the clinical department of TÜV SÜD can provide further feedback.

Regarding standardisation efforts, in the view of TÜV SÜD the creation of a harmonized ISO standard for In-Silico testing of medical devices would tremendously help, or the completion of an already existing relevant standard is another option, since market authorization can in most cases be granted when applicable harmonized standards are appropriately followed.

Other regulatory stakeholder consultations

Liaison with regulatory authorities

Beside the feedback gathered during the RAB meeting (see previous section), various other institutions at stake in the regulatory process of new therapies were consulted during the first reporting period of the project to reflect on how to advance computational modelling and simulations for health product development, assess expectations, interests, needs and requirements, through various ways:

Notified body task force and standard offices: Notified bodies have been assessed via participation in the Avicenna Alliance NB task force, notably allowing regular interactions with DIN. The VPHi has also invited members of different NBs and standard authorities (BSI Medical device and National Standards Authority of Ireland) to discuss during informal consultations.

EMA-Task Force: VPHi's executive director has bimonthly informal interactions with the modelling liaisons of European National Regulators involved in the EMA. There are regular formal meetings with EMA representatives too (e.g., VPHi's Triple Helix Expertise Exchange Workshop April 2021).

Good simulation task force: Members of SIMCor actively participates in the definition of good simulation practice (GSP) as part of the in-silico world community of practice. Via the AA GSP task force, the document is sent to FDA, chapter by chapter, to gather feedback (feedback on two chapters already received, revisions on-going).

The various recommendations and lessons learned through the interactions with other regulatory bodies, as understood by the consortium's partners, are summarised here below.

Recommendations and & lessons learned

- Notified Bodies and standardisation bodies are aware they need to improve their knowledge related to the use of in silico technologies for/in medical devices. Some representatives are actively involved in advocating for the development of guidelines for that purpose. But they are currently facing an overwhelming backlog of work due to the approval and the re-approval of medical devices under the new MDR, which entered in application May 2021. This makes it difficult for them to collaborate in the development of guidelines for assessment of in silico model credibility. Although, recent agreements with the European Commission aim at facilitating the transition to the MDR for NBs and should alleviate that issue in the future. Their level of awareness about in silico technologies remains scarce but notified bodies have indicated the need for (certified) training on silico methods.
- EMA has indicated a strong interest in jointly establishing guidelines for the credibility assessment of digital evidence. Despite the conceptual developments (e.g., joint white paper) and the commitment to considering in silico technologies beyond classical PKPD-PBPK/QSP, there still appears to be a delay in actually moving to the practical implementation. Nonetheless, EMA is welcoming applications for qualification advice.
- There is an interest of regulators to co-design prescriptive guidelines and standards for assessing computational models and digital evidence and ensuring patient's safety and quality of care.
- The establishment and endorsement of standards and guidelines are necessary for notified bodies to be able to accept and assess in-silico-based evidence.
- Awareness must be raised and trust built among clinical opinion leaders and biostatisticians in charge of clinical evaluation in regulatory bodies (not only in clinics).

Conclusion and future actions

The SIMCor consortium successfully consulted various stakeholders to collect regulatory feedback and assess possible regulatory paths for digital evidence. There is a clear opportunity for the consortium to start a working group with the FDA for the development of standards about the virtual cohorts as well as (image) data processing for error minimization. Follow up actions with that regard will be considered. This could eventually lead to the translation of the specific SIMCor SOPs towards a more generic standard and joint publication for the in-silico community. In silico evidence may be accepted by notified bodies without standards (opinion varies among NBs), which could be evaluated through actual submission and collection of feedback by clinical teams, but all agree that the existence of such standards (e.g., harmonized ISO) would tremendously help. In any case, community-based standards and guidelines must be endorsed by regulators for notified bodies to rely on them. Hence the activities carried out by projects such as SIMCor are essential.

In addition, it is important to clearly define a context of use for the SIMCor virtual cohort and computational models and simulations (including simulation of bench test and pre-clinical phases). The level to which it is intended to replace regular clinical studies should be clarified. Ideally, a follow-up correspondence with the clinical team and opinion leaders of TÜV SÜD could help evaluate the feasibility and raise awareness. The consortium will also consider applying for MDDT advice at FDA to get detailed feedback on the intended purposes of the virtual cohort and computational cardiovascular models⁴.

⁴ <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-device-development-tools-mddt>

Appendices

Appendix I – RAB Agenda

I Regulatory Advisory Board (RAB)

Friday 15 June 2022, 14:00 – 16:00 CET, Teams

Participants

Advisory board members	Prasanna Hariharan, <i>Food and Drug Association</i> Jan Kufner, <i>TÜV SÜD</i>
Consortium members	Titus Kühne, Jan Brüning, Leonid Goubergrits, Anja Hennemuth, <i>Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin</i> (CHA) Anna Rizzo, Mirko De Maldè, Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Davide Zaccagnini, <i>Lynkeus</i> (LYN) Andreas Arndt, <i>Biotronik</i> (BIO) Christian Ohmann, <i>European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network</i> (ECRIN) Thomas Czypionka, <i>Institut für Höhere Studien – Institute for Advanced Studies</i> (IHS) Michael Stiehm, Finja Borowski, <i>Institut für ImplantatTechnologie und Biomaterialien e.V.</i> (IIB) Valentina Lavezzo, <i>Philips Electronics Netherlands B.V.</i> (PHI) Wouter Huberts, <i>Technische Universiteit Eindhoven</i> (TUE) Malte Rolf-Pissarczyk, <i>Technical University Graz</i> (TUG) Lucian Itu, Alex Cracanel, <i>Universitatea Transilvania Din Braşov</i> (UTBV) Silvia Schievano, Claudio Capelli, <i>University College of London</i> (UCL) Liesbet Geris, Raphaelle Lesage, <i>Virtual Physiological Human Institute</i> (VPH)

Agenda

Time	Details	Lead
14:00 – 14:10	Greetings and introduction	Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)
14:10 - 14:20	SIMCor: overview and 18-month activity summary Overview of project mission and objectives, summary of the first reporting period activity	
14:20 – 14:30	Virtual cohort generation and validation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Aortic valve disease (AVD)</i> ● <i>Heart failure (HF)</i> 	Wouter Huberts (TUE)
14:30 – 14:40	Virtual device modelling and simulation for virtual device implantation and assessment of device effects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI)</i> 	Michael Stiehm (IIB) Andreas Arndt (BIO)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Pulmonary artery pressure sensors (PAPS)</i> 	
14:40 – 14:50	Standard operating procedures (SOP) definition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Data acquisition for in-silico models</i> ● <i>Data processing for in-silico models</i> ● <i>Guidelines for documentation</i> 	Raphaelle Lesage, Liesbet Geris (VPH)
14:50 – 15:50	Q&A session	Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)
15:50 – 16:00	Final wrap up	Jan Brüning (CHA) Anna Rizzo (LYN)

Appendix II – Preparatory questions for the RAB

Regulatory Advisory Board

Jan Kufner, TÜV SÜD
Prasanna Hariharan, FDA

About the SOPs:

- To which extent, this kind of community based-standard operating procedures (SOP) can serve the realisation of harmonised guidelines, standards, or recommendations for in silico model development verification and validation.
- What is your opinion on the delivered SOPs and recommendations we produced (D4.2 and D4.4)
- Do you have any advice, recommendations or expectations for the next SOPs that we will develop on 1) Virtual Cohort Generation, 2) in silico analysis of TAVI 3) Validation of model predictions on clinical endpoints?
- Is there any initiatives or efforts you would recommend us to participate in, in line with standard creation for model developers.

Modelling and simulation in general:

- The National Cancer Institute (NCI) Community Hub (by Prasanna Hariharan) initiated and published valuable CFD validation benchmarks (benchmark nozzle and blood pump, https://ncihub.org/wiki/FDA_CFD). **Are there any other benchmarks planned, for example a benchmark which covers the pulsatile condition of the cardiovascular system? Can we make suggestions for further benchmark cases, if yes, how and to whom can we do this?**
- Various V&V initiatives are available (FDA draft “Assessing the Credibility of Computational Modeling and Simulation in Medical Device Submissions”, V&V40, NASA Technical Handbook NASA-HDBK-7009A) in which the assessment of the model risk is one essential part. **How can we connect the risk of a model and the required V&V activities?**
- Do you agree with the methodology of model development and validation?
- Do you agree with the methodology for testing implants in silico?